

The Everlasting Debate: School Consolidation in Vermont in the 19th, 20th, and 21st Century

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Introduction

In 1878, Martha Thompson was teaching at a rural school in North Hyde Park, Vermont¹. At this school, the older students were chewing tobacco, and some of the older students had also given young children tobacco to chew as well. The students' use of tobacco annoyed her, but she was especially mad at the students who had given young children the tobacco. She went to find two or three pipes, and then she stuffed them full of tobacco. She brought the pipes back to the class, and she forced every last one of the children who had engaged in the activity, indiscriminately of age, to smoke a pipe. Parents were outraged, but many others excused this action as necessary, or just a mistake. Some students nearly died.²

"Miss Thompson is a fine teacher, of natural good sense and judgment."

- The Lamoille News, 1878³

¹ "North Hyde Park," The Lamoille News, January 3, 1878.

² "Locals," *The Lamoille News*, January 3, 1878.

³ *Ibid*², 1

The paper will cover a school board's blatant attempt to ignore the constitution of Vermont, a controversial piece of legislation that divided the entire state — but effectively did nothing, a governor's political campaign that tried to stay as far away from this legislation as possible, and finally the paper will cover current events in Vermont. This paper will seek to prove that adopting a model of state federalism⁴ in Vermont, in the context of school consolidation, led to debates over school consolidation to occur in local districts, rather than at the state level.

⁴ “Federalism,” LII / Legal Information Institute (Cornell Law School), accessed February 4, 2022, <https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/federalism#:~:text=Overview>.

Before Consolidation

The introduction showcased an incredible amount of neglect, and even abuse within the school system of Vermont. While at the time some people, such as the editor of The Lamoille News, did widely accept this, others did not. This neglect was the center of attention on the debate around education, and the method that many proposed to fix this was school consolidation.⁵ School consolidation is the practice of closing down schools and combining them into a singular school.⁶

One of these towns was Middlebury, for which many of its citizens had been advocating for consolidation since 1866. The reason given was primarily economic, but most parents also believed that their children would get a better education. In 1866, a resolution passed to consolidate schools. An article in the Middlebury Register that covered this meeting read, “let each district vote at a regularly called meeting in favor of consolidation, then let a town meeting be called which has full power to consolidate the two districts, and the greatest difficulties in the way of a graded school is removed.”⁷

That last excerpt shows two things. The first is that the article was written from a perspective in favor of consolidation, where it talks about removing difficulties in education.

⁵ William Mathis, “The History of School Consolidation Battles,” VTDigger, September 8, 2015, <https://vtdigger.org/2015/09/08/william-mathis-the-history-of-school-consolidation-battles/>.

⁶ Erik Nelson, “School Consolidation. ERIC Digest,” www.ericdigests.org (ERIC Clearinghouse on Educational Management, 1985), <https://www.ericdigests.org/pre-925/school.htm>.

⁷ “Middlebury Graded School,” Middlebury Register, April 9, 1866.

Understanding this bias in the article is important for understanding what is meant by “full power to consolidate.” The meaning is not objectively that meetings held between school districts have the power to override accepted interpretations of the state law, but it was that they were going to ignore any possible constitutional or legal issues and consolidate without the consent of the state government.

This was a gray area because in 1777 section HL was added to the constitution of Vermont which read: “A school or schools shall be established in each town, by the legislature, for the convenient instruction of youth, with such salaries to the masters, paid by each town, making proper use of school lands in each town, thereby to enable them to instruct youth at low prices. One grammar school in each county, and one university in this State, ought to be established by direction of the General Assembly.”⁸

In the 1793 Constitution, this amendment was removed⁹, but that didn’t change the fact that school districts were still established by the legislature. The state maintained the power to legislate school districts, so school districts probably did not actually have the authority to do this. Additionally, there was legislation still in effect that was passed in 1782 irrespective of section HL.¹⁰ This makes it seem like the state government is actively controlling the school district. Essentially, this means that the Middlebury Graded School actively tried to override the state government of Vermont.

⁸ “Vermont Constitution” (1777).

⁹ “Vermont Constitution” (1793).

¹⁰ John A. Williams, “Laws of Vermont”(1965).

Perhaps the semi unconstitutional ploy could have succeeded, however, the Middlebury Graded School certainly was not united around this issue by any respect. The same article notes that there was substantial opposition: “the speaker predicted te adoption of the plan at any rate, either in a kindly spirit or otherwise, and he counseled moderation on all sides in order to prevent the kindling of unfriendly feelings which might remain interminable to annoy an neutralize all efforts for progress and reform.”¹¹ It is more than clear that there certainly were “unfriendly” feelings, but more than this it shows that the advocates for the plan knew that this was not over.

The fears were realized, and the half illegal ploy did not work out. The debates in Middlebury continued into the late 1940s — late enough to have movies screened in full color about the issue. One of these movies was called, “A Way of Life.” The film was part of a series that was meant to “show how consolidation has worked out in other places,”¹² and the purpose of these screenings was to advocate for consolidation because even though the Middlebury graded school was one of the first schools in Vermont to have debates around consolidation, it did not actually consolidate.

The Middlebury Graded School is just one of the more extreme examples of schools that opposed the anti-consolidation position of the Vermont state, but there were many other

¹¹ Ibid⁷, 3

¹²“Film on School Consolidation Shown Tonight.” *Addison County Independent*, October 21, 1949.

examples as well. In fact, the sentiment of the legislature was changing as well, and in an outgoing speech in 1892, Gov. Page talked a lot about the issue.

“Gov. Page is well prepared to present in a clear, intelligent and practicable manner the needs of the State, and his recommendations deserve the careful attention which they are pretty sure to receive. He makes a strong plea for the general adoption of the system of town supervision of schools and expresses the belief that the time is not far distant when it will be adopted. It is doubtful whether a majority of the members of the legislature will favor the passage of an entirely new school law at this session in view of the fact that the system now in use has been given hardly a fair trial. That the present law is imperfect, however, its firmest friends will not claim and it will need radical revision.”¹³

Gov. Page clearly supported this legislation, and viewed it as one of the most important issues that Vermont faced. Undoubtedly, if left up to him, the legislation would pass, but Page’s time in office was over, and the incoming Gov. Fuller would have the power to either sign or veto the legislation.

¹³ “Gov. Page’s Valedictory.” The Burlington Free Press, October 7, 1892.

The Vicious Act

In 1892, a new law was proposed, known as the “Vicious Act of 1892.”¹⁴ It was named this because it mandated every single town in the state of Vermont to consolidate into one district — although there was actually no mandate within the legislation. Large cities were perfectly capable of bearing the financial burden that came from education, but rural school districts were struggling to finance education. If the legislation were to be passed, it would inevitably transfer much of this financial burden to rural schools that were already struggling, and because they did not have the resources to implement consolidation, this could make the situation even worse. The key thing to understand here is that this was met with substantial resistance for the economic issues already mentioned. But also many parents did not want this new model of standardized education to be forced on them because they feared that this would harm the quality of education.¹⁵

On the other hand, there were many perceived benefits to consolidation and the Vicious Act. Consolidation could provide any district with the necessary number of schools, so schools would not be strained for resources. It got rid of unfair taxes that forced people in rural towns to give an exorbitant amount of taxes towards schools. There were many debates around district lines, and it would completely eliminate them. It was also believed that consolidation

¹⁴ “No. 20 of the Acts of 1892 of the State of Vermont”, Burlington, *The Free Press Association*

¹⁵ *Ibid*⁵, 3

could prevent local arguments. It lowered costs for schools generally because consolidation is more efficient. School teaching would become more standardized. It ensured that fewer teachers could be employed as class sizes were traditionally larger under consolidation. Additionally, it allowed for higher quality teaching because individual teachers could be paid more, and this is a preferable alternative to employing young inexperienced teachers that could often be as young as 15 or 16.¹⁶

Governor Fuller's Position

Both sides held strong positions on consolidation, and this put the incoming governor into a challenging political position. If he pushed for consolidation, he would alienate many of his voters, but if he pushed against it, he would alienate them. In the present day, polling could offer a very simple solution to this problem, and Gov. Fuller could have simply endorsed the more popular plan. Polling was a thing, but it was not nearly as accurate as it is now, and it would have been possible to conduct an accurate poll accounting for the various different groups across Vermont.¹⁷

This political predicament meant that Gov. Fuller needed another method to deal with the controversy, but he was a clever politician, and he recognized the threat that this issue could

¹⁶ "The Town School System," *ST. Albans Daily Messenger*, November 3, 1882.

¹⁷ D. SUNSHINE HILLYGUS, "THE EVOLUTION of ELECTION POLLING in the UNITED STATES," *Public Opinion Quarterly* 75, no. 5 (2011): 16–17.

pose to his political career. In Fuller's inaugural speech he addressed the issue, and the Burlington Free Press summarized this speech that was given directly after former Gov. Page's.

“While Gov. Fuller does not believe in changing our State system of education too frequently, he urges upon the Legislature the duty of devising ways and means to further elevate the standing of the schools of the State. He holds that the town system of supervision would give the best results, but he recognized the fact that it would work hardship to some of the smaller districts in the more sparsely settled communities.”¹⁸

Gov. Fuller was attempting to avoid this controversy entirely, and in the speech he does not take a position. Instead, Fuller simply urges the legislature to make policies that will benefit Vermont schools. Benefit is also never defined because this would indicate support for a position. When he elaborated, all he said was that the current system would be best, but in rural communities it would be bad. Because of the nature of the debate, this is an entirely non-committal position. One position values the economies of cities over passing consolidation that may not even work. The other position stated that it was nearly impossible to educate children effectively if consolidation was not implemented.¹⁹ In his speech, Fuller just parroted both points, but never explicitly endorses one over the other. This was a political maneuver to push the controversy entirely onto the legislature. Whatever the legislature said, Fuller was going to parrot to maintain political capital.²⁰

¹⁸ “Gov. Fuller’s Message,” *The Burlington Free Press*, October 7, 1892.

¹⁹ *Ibid*¹⁴, 7

²⁰ Gabriele Gratton, Richard Holden, and Barton Lee, “Political Capital,” *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3363382>.

When the legislature passed the proposed plan, Gov. Fuller stuck to his strategy, and the legislation passed without a veto.²¹

After The Vicious Act

The first effect of the passing the Vicious Act of 1892 was a serious conflict in Vermont, hence the name, however Gov. Fuller did not admit this in his 1984 valedictory speech. “Gov. Fuller finds that the adoption of the town system of schools had caused but slight friction, and the report of the State superintendent indicates a decided improvement, which leads the retiring governor to conclude that but slight changes will be necessary in the school law.”²²

Debates around consolidation that can be directly attributed to this Act continued well into the 1960s. But this debate was not over whether to abolish the law. There was actually no mandate present within the legislation to implement it, and as a result, only 16 towns in the entirety of Vermont attempted to implement this voluntarily.²³ Because there was no mandate in the legislation, debates continued, but under the new law, they were fought on a local level with individual or multiple school boards.²⁴

²¹ Ibid¹⁶, 8

²² “Gov. Fuller’s Valedictory.” *The Burlington Free Press*, October 7, 1894.

²³ Ruth Zinar, “Educational Problems in Rural Vermont, 1875–1900: A Not So Distant Mirror,” *Vermont History* 51(1983):197–220, 200

²⁴ “School Consolidation Dilemma,” *The Bennington Banner*, January 31, 1964.

Conclusion

It is impossible to say which side is correct about the consolidation debate because it never ended, and is still going on to this day.²⁵ New legislation called Act 46 passed recently, and the goal of it is to consolidate schools to create “larger and more efficient school governance structures.”²⁶ Just as it has been for well over a hundred years, there is still opposition to consolidation in Vermont, but Act 46 made a major change. The precedent set by The Vicious Act was to let districts and towns decide on their own whether to consolidate, but Act 46 changed that, and mandated that school districts consolidate. This has been extremely controversial. Multiple school districts have fought back, and one was allowed to leave a consolidated union after a successful campaign.²⁷

Again, it is too early to know the long-term effects of this, but what this paper shows is that the model of state federalism embraced by The Vicious Act nearly immediately shifted debate around consolidation onto individual districts, but not the entire state. Before 1892, this

²⁵ Megan James, “Editorial: Small Towns vs. State Board: Only One’s on Target,” Addison Independent, January 27, 2022, <https://www.addisonindependent.com/2022/01/27/editorial-small-towns-vs-state-board-only-ones-on-target/>.

²⁶ “Act 46: State Board of Education’s Final Report of Decisions and Order | Agency of Education,” Vermont.gov, 2010, <https://education.vermont.gov/vermont-schools/school-governance/act-46-state-board-final-plan>.

²⁷ Lola Duffort, “Having Gained Independence, Ripton Now Considers Re-Merging,” VTDigger, September 17, 2021, <https://vtdigger.org/2021/09/17/having-gained-independence-ripton-now-considers-re-merging/>.

was not the case, and because the state government gave the individual school districts some level of autonomy, conflict at the state level stopped. Even today, this is still playing out in Vermont where the precedent has been undone, and now state level debates are restarting.

Annotated Bibliography:

Primary

“Film on School Consolidation Shown Tonight.” *Addison County Independent*, October 21, 1949.

This source describes an event where 2 films about school consolidation were played in color as an attempt to promote the idea of school consolidation. It demonstrates a sharp contrast with a lot of the other sources from other time periods, and it demonstrates how long school consolidation was an issue for.

“Gov. Fuller’s Message,” *The Burlington Free Press*, October 7, 1892.

Gov. Fuller was elected in the 1892 gubernatorial election in Vermont, and this source is a summary of the speech that he gave directly after former Gov. Fuller’s Valedictory speech.

“Gov. Fuller’s Valedictory.” *The Burlington Free Press*, October 7, 1894.

In 1894 Gov. Fuller gave his valedictory speech, and this source is a summary of that. Fuller talks about school consolidation and the passage of the Vicious Act.

“Gov. Page’s Valedictory.” *The Burlington Free Press*, October 7, 1892.

Gov. Page gave his valedictory speech in 1892 where he advocated for the passage of The Vicious Act of 1892, and this was especially important because Fuller was undecided on the issue.

“Locals,” *The Lamoille News*, January 3, 1878.

This source tells the Story of Martha Thompson, a school teacher in Hyde Park, Vermont. She gave tobacco to children as a punishment for smoking tobacco, and some of the the children almost died. While the paper did oppose the action, it also excused her and said it was surprising that she made such a mistake because she had good judgment. This was used for the introduction, and was relevant for the rest of the piece because it showed the poor conditions, and inadequate teachers that rural schools had to deal with before consolidation, or at least it was perceived by many that a lack of consolidation was to blame for this. The quote was taken slightly out of context, and it is directly saying that they are surprised that she made a mistake because she had such great judgment, but the general sentiment of the quote still applies even in context because she obviously did not have good judgment, and the fact that it is saying that this was a mistake does not diminish from the fact that they also say that she has good sense, and judgment. The main point here is that even after she did this, the editor of the *Lamoille News* still believes she has good sense and judgment.

“Middlebury Graded School,” *Middlebury Register*, April 9, 1866.

This article tells the story of a meeting that took place regarding the Middlebury Graded School. The school essentially attempted to circumvent the law in Vermont to pursue consolidation — although the source itself is biased and tries to deny this fact. (later backed up with several sources confirming that this is a very biased source)

“No. 20 of the Acts of 1892 of the State of Vermont”, *The Burlington Free Press Association*

This source simply details the Vicious Act of 1892, and the fact that it was passed.

“North Hyde Park,” *The Lamoille News*, January 3, 1878.

This source confirms some extra information about Martha Thompson, and it details how she started teaching at the select school in Hyde Park.

“School Consolidation Dilemma,” *The Bennington Banner*, January 31, 1964.

This source proves that the Vicious Act was not a mandate, and it gives a specific example of local debate after the Vicious Act was passed. The source specifically advocates against mandates proposed by Gov. Hoff which is not specifically talked about in the paper, but just the fact that these mandates have not been implemented.

“The Town School System,” *ST. Albans Daily Messenger*, November 3, 1882.

This is probably the most important primary source in the entire paper. It gives a comprehensive list of given advantages, and disadvantages of school consolidation, and it ties directly into the theme. The article also appears to be unbiased, and it compares multiple different viewpoints which makes it a great source to actually weigh the values of the different sides in this debate over policy against each other.

“Vermont Constitution” (1777).

This source was used to make a constitutional argument about the Middlebury source, and why I believe this to be unconstitutional under the former HL that was abolished, but still theoretically gave the states power to control schools (this is also backed up through other sources that show that state government making laws regarding school districts).

“Vermont Constitution” (1793).

This simply said that Sec. HL was removed from the constitution.

Secondary

Lola Duffort, “Having Gained Independence, Ripton Now Considers Re-Merging,” *VTDigger*, September 17, 2021, <https://vtdigger.org/2021/09/17/having-gained-independence-ripton-now-considers-re-merging/>.

This source is used to show how consolidation is still contentious today, and how one school ran a campaign to free themselves from a consolidated union, and got out successfully.

Gabriele Gratton, Richard Holden, and Barton Lee, “Political Capital,” *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3363382>.

This source provides a good definition for political capital, that it is a person's ability to effect policy change, and to get re-elected. This is used as the motive for Gov. Fullers comments about school consolidation, or lack thereof.

D. SUNSHINE HILLYGUS, "THE EVOLUTION of ELECTION POLLING in the UNITED STATES," *Public Opinion Quarterly* 75, no. 5 (2011): 16–17.

This source says that polling has gotten much better in the modern era, and it demonstrates that polls would not have been viable in 1892. It also says that this is one of the main differences between political strategy in modern times, and in the past.

Megan James, "Editorial: Small Towns vs. State Board: Only One's on Target," *Addison Independent*, January 27, 2022, <https://www.addisonindependent.com/2022/01/27/editorial-small-towns-vs-state-board-only-ones-on-target/>.

This source details the current fight over consolidation in Vermont,

William Mathis, "The History of School Consolidation Battles," *VT Digger*, September 8, 2015, <https://vtdigger.org/2015/09/08/william-mathis-the-history-of-school-consolidation-battles/>.

This source is about the Consolidation Battles, and was used for an overview of what consolidation actually was.

Erik Nelson, "School Consolidation. ERIC Digest," *www.ericdigests.org* (ERIC Clearinghouse on Educational Management, 1985), <https://www.ericdigests.org/pre-925/school.htm>.

This source just gives a definition of school consolidation, and that is all it is used for.

John A. Williams, "Laws of Vermont"(1965).

The source gives a comprehensive overview of the laws of Vermont, and it is extremely reliable as it was made by a former secretary of state as well. It talks about a law passed in 1782 that affects school which is only relevant to this project because it backs up the legal argument on the illegality of the Middlebury meetings. Even if abolished constitutional amendments don't show the state government controls school districts, this legislation means that the state government is exercising authority over school districts, and thus has a valid claim to prevent consolidation on the basis that they control school districts.

Ruth Zinar, "Educational Problems in Rural Vermont, 1875–1900: A Not So Distant Mirror,"
Vermont History 51(1983):197–220, 200

This source shows how only 16 towns implemented the Vicious Act.

"Act 46: State Board of Education's Final Report of Decisions and Order | Agency of Education,"
Vermont.gov, 2010 <https://education.vermont.gov/vermont-schools/school-governance/act-46-state-board-final-plan>.

Act 46 is a modern day consolidation bill that actually mandates consolidation which is extremely relevant to my thesis which talks about state level federalism. Act 46 changes the precedent set in 1892.

"Federalism," LII / Legal Information Institute (Cornell Law School), accessed February 4, 2022,
<https://www.law.cornell.edu/wex/federalism#:~:text=Overview>.

The way that the word federalism is used in this paper is somewhat unconventional. It simply says "Federalism is a system of government in which the same territory is controlled by two levels of government." While it does specify that this is usually a broad federal government, it does not put a limit on it which is why according to this definition state level federalism is a real thing, as federalism can exist at any level.